

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE HIGH STRAIN RATE DEFORMATION
OF SiCw/2124 Al COMPOSITEJ. Harding and M. Taya*
Department of Engineering Science

and

B. Derby and S. Pickard
Department of Metallurgy and Materials Science
University of Oxford, Parks Road
OXFORD, UK

ABSTRACT

Tensile tests at strain rates from 10^{-3} to 1500/s, using a split Hopkinson's pressure bar at the impact rates, have been performed on SiCw/2124 Al metal matrix composite specimens with fibre volume fractions of 15% and 25%. The effect of strain rate on the modulus, flow stress and elongation to failure is determined. Optical, scanning electron and transmission electron microscopy are used to examine the deformation and fracture processes. A small strain-rate dependence of the flow stress is observed and a more marked effect on the elongation to failure.

INTRODUCTION

The effect of high strain rate on the mechanical behaviour of metal matrix composites has received little attention. Previously published studies have been concerned with the residual strength of an as-impacted plate [1,2] made from a continuous fibre metal matrix composite material and a study of the microscopic fracture processes in a particulate metal matrix composite plate subjected to high velocity impact in a direction perpendicular to the plane of the plate [3]. In this latter investigation Taya et al. found that the nucleation of voids under high strain rates occurred at only a small fraction of the particles whereas previously it had been found [4] that at quasi-static rates voids nucleated at almost all the particle sites. As far as is known, no work has yet been reported on the impact behaviour of short fibre metal matrix composite such as the SiC whisker/aluminium matrix system to be studied here.

This investigation seeks to determine the stress-strain response of a short fibre metal matrix composite material having a 2124 aluminium alloy matrix reinforced with SiC whiskers in volume fractions of 15% and 25%.

*On leave from the Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Washington, FU-10, Seattle, WA 98195, USA.

Tests will be performed at room temperature and strain rates from quasi-static ($\sim 10^{-3}$ /s) to impact (~ 1500 /s). At the impact rates a split Hopkinson's pressure bar system will be used, in the modified form recently developed [5] for the tensile impact testing of continuous fibre reinforced composites with polymeric matrices.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES AND SPECIMEN MATERIALS

Three different types of testing machine were used in this investigation, a standard screw-driven Instron loading machine for tests at a quasi-static rate of $\sim 10^{-3}$ /s, a hydraulically-operated loading machine [6] for tests at an intermediate rate of ~ 10 /s and an impact loading machine, employing a gas gun to accelerate the projectile [7], for tests at strain rates of ~ 1000 /s. The same design of cylindrical test specimen was used at all strain rates. In tests at the low and intermediate rates the integrated output from a pair of linear variable differential transformers in parallel with the specimen was used to determine the specimen strain. In tests at impact rates a split Hopkinson pressure bar was used and the strain determined from one-dimensional elastic wave theory. Neither technique, however, gives an accurate measure of the specimen elastic deformation. To allow, therefore, a more accurate measure of the effect of fibre volume fraction and strain rate on the tensile modulus and strain at yield the specimen elastic strain was also determined by means of a pair of strain gauges attached directly to the specimen parallel gauge section.

Specimens were machined from 6mm thick plate material with the tensile axis in the extrusion direction, along which the majority of the short fibres were aligned. Some difficulty was experienced in obtaining a good surface finish in the specimen gauge region and fillets and this may partly explain the tendency for specimens to fail close to the fillets. Two plates were fabricated by a powder metallurgical technique and supplied by the ARCO Chemical Company with fibre volume fractions of either 15% or 25%. The matrix was 2124 aluminium alloy in the standard T6 heat treated condition and the fibres were SiC whiskers typically of length $5\mu\text{m}$ and diameter $0.7\mu\text{m}$. A scanning electron micrograph of the 25% SiC material is shown in fig.1 at a magnification of 1400x. Chemical etching was used to make the SiC whiskers more visible.

Fig.1 Microstructure of as-received 25%SiC Material (x1400)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A minimum of three tests was performed on each material at each strain rate. Impact tests were performed at two different gas-gun reservoir pressures but the resulting average strain rate differed by less than a factor of 2 so all these tests have been taken together and the mean result quoted for each material. Stress-strain curves for 15%SiC specimens are shown in fig. 2a at strain rates of 2.5×10^{-3} /s, the mean of 3 tests, 20/s, the mean also of 3 tests, and 1500/s, the mean of 7 tests. Similar curves for 25%SiC specimens are shown in fig.2b at strain rates of 9×10^{-4} /s, the mean of 4 tests, 10/s, the mean of 3 tests, and 900/s, the mean of 6 tests. For both fibre volume fractions the strain at failure increases continuously with increasing strain rate while the flow stress at a given plastic strain is lowest for tests at the intermediate rate and highest at the impact rate. This is an anomalous result, quite different from the behaviour generally observed in tests on a wide range of materials. A more usual response, found, for example, in heat treated alloys with a relatively high quasi-static strength such as 2124 aluminium alloy in the T6 condition, is for the flow stress to be rate independent at low to medium rates of strain and only to show a small increase at impact rates of strain. The present results for the 15%SiC specimens could be described in this way, since the difference between the stress-strain curves at the quasi-static and the intermediate rates is so small, but this is not the case for the 25%SiC specimens where the difference is much more marked.

A clearer indication of the significance of these apparent effects of strain rate is obtained from fig.3, which shows the variation of the yield, flow and ultimate stresses with the logarithm of the average strain rate during the test for both materials. Flow stresses are determined at plastic strains of $\frac{1}{2}$, 1 and 2%. At the low and intermediate strain rates failure occurs while the load is still increasing so the ultimate stress is also the fracture stress. In the impact tests the exact point of failure is less clearly defined and may follow, rather than coincide with, the ultimate stress. The experimental scatter band and the number of specimens tested

Fig.2 Effect of Strain Rate on Tensile Stress-Strain Curves

are quoted for each testing condition in fig.3. For the 15%SiC material a clear effect of strain rate on the yield stress is observed, although the difficulty of defining the yield point with sufficient precision leads to a large scatter band in the impact tests. A similar trend is seen in the 25% SiC material except that here the experimental scatter is large in tests at all three strain rates. A strain-rate dependence is also very clearly observed in the flow stress at $\frac{1}{2}\%$ plastic strain for both materials and, in particular, the marked reduction in flow stress for the 25%SiC specimens at the intermediate rate is confirmed. At higher plastic strains the same trends continue but the significance is reduced as the rate dependence of the flow stress becomes of the same order as the experimental scatter.

In previous work on fibre-reinforced polymeric-matrix composites a very marked increase in tensile elastic modulus has sometimes been observed [5]. As may be seen from fig.4, a smaller, but still significant, effect of strain rate on the tensile modulus is observed in both the materials studied here. For the 15%SiC specimens the modulus is rate independent below $\sim 20/s$ but then increases by about 20% as the strain rate is raised to $\sim 1000/s$ whereas for the 25%SiC specimens the modulus falls by about 25% between the low and intermediate strain rate tests and then increases by $\sim 40\%$ in the impact tests, reflecting the behaviour of the flow stress at low plastic strains in this

Fig.3 Strain-Rate Dependence of Yield and Flow Stresses

Fig.4 Strain-Rate Dependence of Tensile Modulus

Fig.5 Strain-Rate Dependence of Failure Strain

material. Since a rate dependent elastic modulus would seem to imply a significant level of microstrain in the elastic region a general correlation between the rate dependence of the modulus and of the flow stress at low plastic strains is not unreasonable. A more detailed explanation of this anomalous behaviour, however, is more difficult to provide.

For both materials the stress-strain curves of fig.2 showed a continuous increase in fracture strain with strain rate. This is confirmed in fig.5, which shows the variation of fracture strain with the logarithm of strain rate for both materials. Two estimates of the fracture strain are given, the first from a measure of the increase in length when the broken pieces of specimen are reassembled and the second from the computed stress-strain curve for the test. The first method usually gives the higher estimate and tends to have a low accuracy for the more brittle specimens, particularly those which break into more than two pieces, as happened in one intermediate rate test and four impact tests. The accuracy of the second method is reduced in the impact tests by the difficulty of determining with confidence the point of fracture on the specimen transmitted stress-time signal. In a few impact tests, however, the specimen strain gauges continued to record up to the point of failure and provided a check on the fracture strain determined by the second method.

As is clear in fig.5, both estimates of fracture strain show the same well marked increase with strain rate, from ~4% to ~8% for the 15%SiC specimens and from ~1% to ~3% for the 25%SiC specimens. Possible reasons for this increase will be discussed in the light of the metallurgical examination of the specimens after testing, as presented in the following section.

METALLOGRAPHIC STUDIES

Longitudinal sections were taken through the 15%SiC specimens after testing at a quasi-static and an impact rate and examined to determine the extent of void formation. In contrast to earlier work [3,4] no voids were detected away from the fracture surface at either rate of loading. Close to the fracture surface, however, extensive cracking and void formation were seen in the impacted specimen, see fig.6a, but not in that tested at the quasi-static rate, see fig.6b. It has not been possible yet to repeat the examination for the 25%SiC specimens.

Scanning electron microscopy was used to examine the fracture surfaces of the two types of specimen tested at both the quasi-static and the impact rates. Typical micrographs for a quasi-static test on a 15%SiC specimen and an impact test on a 25%SiC specimen are shown in fig.7. Cup-and-cone type dimples, implying a ductile failure mode, are seen to predominate in all such micrographs and are frequently found to be associated with the SiC whiskers, suggesting that the voids are probably nucleated at the fibre/matrix interface, presumably at the fibre ends. Growth and coalescence of these voids could then provide the mechanism of final failure. From the evidence of the scanning electron fractographs this mechanism applies to both materials at all strain rates and so it does not explain the increase in overall strain to fracture with increasing strain rate.

TEM studies were undertaken only on the 15%SiC material for an untested specimen and for specimens after testing at a quasi-static and an impact rate. Foils were prepared from thin discs cut perpendicular to the axis of the spec-

a) Impact tested specimen

b) Quasi-statically tested specimen

Fig.6 Optical Micrographs of Fracture Region in 15%SiC Specimens (800x)

Fig.7 Scanning Electron Fractographs

a) 15%SiC Specimen (4200x)

b) 25%SiC Specimen (4500x)

imen, i.e. to the extrusion direction, so that the majority of SiC whiskers are also perpendicular to the plane of the disc. For the fractured specimens the discs were cut at a distance of about 1mm from the fracture surface. Typical transmission electron micrographs obtained in this way for undeformed, quasi-statically loaded and impact loaded specimens are shown in fig.8. The typical end view of a SiC whisker, hexagonal in cross-section, is seen in each. An increased dislocation density is apparent after quasi-static testing over that observed in both the undeformed and the impact tested specimens. This result is confirmed by measurements of the dislocation density over some ten different regions in each of the three specimens. Although the local value of dislocation density varied quite widely, average values for each material of 5×10^9 , 3×10^{10} and $5 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for undeformed, quasi-statically loaded and impact loaded specimens respectively were obtained.

Fig.8 Transmission Electron Micrographs
(15%SiC specimens)

a) Undeformed specimen (52500x)

b) Quasi-statically loaded specimen (63000x)

c) Impact loaded specimen (52500x)

DISCUSSION

All specimens failed without any sign of necking or of significant macroscopic plastic deformation at overall elongations no greater than 10%. In all cases, however, the fracture surfaces showed ductile dimples and signs of void formation such as are usually associated with extensive plastic deformation in the necked regions of materials containing non-deformable particles when voids nucleate in regions of high strain concentration and correspondingly high dislocation density. The present TEM studies did indeed show the highest local dislocation densities close to the surface of the whiskers. This was true even in the undeformed material where the probable cause was a large local stress due to thermal mismatch between the matrix and the whisker. It was not necessary, therefore, to impose by mechanical loading a large overall plastic strain in order to obtain the condition for void nucleation and ductile failure at the local level in the present specimens.

Although this may explain the observed ductile fracture surface in specimens which showed at the macroscopic level an essentially brittle behaviour, complications arise when the effect of strain rate is considered. From the stress-strain curves shown in fig.2 it is apparent that for both materials the initial strength and the strain to failure are significantly increased between the quasi-static and the impact rate of strain. This is a surprising result which conflicts with the more usual observation that increasing strength is accompanied by a reduction in ductility. It also conflicts with the observation that the dislocation density, on average, is lower after impact testing than after quasi-static loading, implying a lower plastic strain generally in the impacted specimens. As noted earlier, accurate determination of the failure strain, particularly in the impact tests, was difficult. However several different estimates of the failure strain were made and, despite some discrepancies between the various estimates, the general trends in all cases were the same. The accuracy of the dislocation density measurements also needs to be considered in view of the wide variations in the local value from one region of the specimen to another. An attempt is being made, therefore, to corroborate the TEM findings by observing whether an increase in the intensity of the surface slip markings, indicative of more dislocation movement, can be detected after quasi-static loading. This requires pre-polishing the specimen surfaces before testing and then examining for signs of slip after testing. We hope that the results of this further study will be available by the time of the conference.

Assuming the increase in fracture strain and the decrease in dislocation density for the impact tested specimens to be genuine effects it would seem necessary to relate the increased deformation to damage mechanisms involving an increase in volume rather than to plastic flow at a constant volume. Such mechanisms might include micro-cracking or void formation which would need to play a bigger part in the overall deformation process at high strain rates than under quasi-static loading. Certainly the fracture surface area was often greater in tests at the intermediate and impact rates where several specimens broke at more than one place and where, in general, the overall fracture strain tended to be higher than in those specimens which broke at only one place. Also, as shown in fig.6a, significant void formation was observed close to the fracture surface in an impact test but not, see fig. 6b, after quasi-static loading. This conflicts with the earlier results of Taya et al. [3] who found a reduced void formation under high rate deformation, although this was for a particulate system under a different type of impact loading. In the present impact tests rough estimates suggest that

voids could only account for about a 1% strain increase over that in the quasi-static tests, rather than the 3 to 4% required. It is possible, however, see fig.6a, that surface voiding was more extensive than is immediately apparent, such that some voided material had already broken away before fracture was completed and only the residual surface material remains available for examination.

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile tests at strain rates from 10^{-3} to 1500/s have been performed on SiCw/2124 Al short fibre composite specimens with reinforcement volume fractions of 15% and 25%. Both types of specimen showed a small increase in flow stress between the quasi-static and the impact rates of strain, although an anomalous reduction in flow stress was shown by the 25%SiC specimens at an intermediate strain rate of ~ 10 /s. Both materials showed a marked increase in fracture strain with increasing strain rate. For the 15%SiC specimens this is tentatively related to extensive void formation close to the fracture surfaces under impact loading. Metallographic studies of void formation are still continuing and it is hoped that further progress will be reported at the conference.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Grateful acknowledgment is made to the Royal Society for the award of a Senior Visiting Fellowship to Professor Taya, to Dr. Lilholt of the Riso National Laboratory, Denmark and Mr. H.S. Yoon of the University of Washington, Seattle for their help in obtaining the SEM photographs and to Mr. M.E. C. Taylor who supervised the mechanical testing programme.

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